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A REVIEW ON ORAL DISPERSIBLE TABLET (ODT).

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ABSTRACT

To improve bioavailability and patient compliance, oral dispersible drug delivery systems are used mostly because Oral dispersible tablets are the novel dosage form which quickly disintegrates in the mouth (1-3 min) without chewing upon oral administration and without the need of water. As compared to conventional tablets and capsules oral dispersible tablets (ODT) are getting the attention from the last three decades because it has better patient compliances, better solubility, and stability. Oral dispersible tablets have a quality that disintegrates rapidly generally in seconds when put on the tongue because it contains mainly medicinal substances in the solid dosage form. This new ODT technology is enhancing the patient life cycle and making a convenient dosing system for pediatric, geriatric, and psychiatric patients with dysphagia because it directly addresses the pharmaceutical and patient needs. This new technology encourages the academic industry to develop a newer orally disintegrating formulation and technology or evaluation methodology which is suitable for drug candidates for its future prospects. Though considerable research has been done in the formulation development and technologies for ODTs, more intensive investigations are to be carried out in this promising area to result in newer cost-effective technologies and better products. The potential of dosage forms is promising because of the availability of new technologies combined with strong market acceptance and patient compliance.

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INTRODUCTION^[1]

The most popular solid dosage forms are being tablets and capsules. One important drawback of such dosage forms is Dysphagia, or difficulty in swallowing is common among all age groups. Common complaints about the difficulty in swallowing tablets are size, surface, and taste of tablets. To fulfill these medical needs, pharmaceutical technologists have developed a novel oral dosage form known as Oral Dispersible Tablets. Direct ingestion is intended in most pharmaceutical dosage forms which are formulated for oral administration. The oral route is the best or convenient way of drug administration for patients and this way issued by most of the therapeutic agents for producing effects of the oral route. A term used by the "European Pharmacopoeia" Oral dispersible Tablet; this tablet is parsed in the mouth within 3 seconds before swallowing it. The oral dispersible tablet also called "ODTs" and it is quickly disintegrating tablet or it dissolves in the mouth quickly because it is a mouth dissolving tablet and also a fast-responding tablet with porous and rapid melting nature. Freezing & drying, tablet molding, spray drying, mass extrusion, sublimation, and direct compression are the conventional methods that are used for the preparation of orally disintegrating tablets. ODTs response time is very fast & its disintegration time is few seconds to a minute and according to the United States, Food and Drug Administration (FDA) ODTs is a Solid forms substance having active ingredient & medicinal substance which dissolve in a mouth Fastly when placed on a tongue in a few seconds. Because, when ODTs come in contact with saliva it releases active drugs that provide maximum drug bioavailability in comparison to conventional dosage form due to this tablet getting dispersed or disintegrated. The hydrophilic nature excipients are used in ODT technology and it is selected on the basis of drug physicochemical property mainly hydrophilicity or hydrophobicity. In saliva, the active agent dissolves rapidly and no matter whatever membrane encounter, unless it is protected by pre-gastric absorption and the current review is aimed to study present development of ODT technology and sustainability of drug candidates and their characterization of ODT.

Biopharmaceutical consideration^[2,3]

When drug delivery system put on, it is must that to consider Biopharmaceutical factor like metabolism and excretion.

Pharmacokinetics

Study has done on absorption, distribution, metabolism and excretion in this consideration. Drug attains therapeutic level after absorption and therefore elicits pharmacological effect, so both rate and extend of absorption is important. There is delay in disintegration and therefore dissolution in conventional dosage form while ODTs is rapidly disintegrates in oral cavity and dissolution is rapid. Due to disintegration of ODTs in mouth absorption in started from mouth, pharynx and esophagus. Some factors like age, GI pH, and blood flow through GI are taken into consideration, because elders may be considered as separate unique Medicare population. There are many factors on which drug distribution depends like tissue permeability, perfusion rate, binding of drug to tissue, disease state, drug interaction etc. In geriatric patients, decrease in body mass and total body water result in decreased volume of distribution of water-soluble drugs and increased volume of distribution (V_d) of lipid soluble drugs. Duration and intensity of action depends upon rate of drug removal from the body or site of action i.e., biotransformation. Decrease in liver volume, regional blood flow to liver reduces the biotransformation of drug through oxidation, reduction and hydrolysis. Excretion by renal clearance is slowed, thus half-life of renal excreted drugs increase.

Pharmacodynamics

Drug receptor interaction impaired in elderly as well as in young adult due to undue development of organ. Decreased ability of the body to respond barro reflexive stimuli, cardiac output, and orthostatic hypotension may see in taking antihypertensive like prazosin. Decreased sensitivity of the CVS to β -adrenergic agonist and antagonist. Immunity is less and taken into consideration while administered antibiotics. Altered response to drug therapy-elderly show diminished bronchodilator effect of theophylline shows increased sensitivity to barbiturates. Concomitant illnesses are often present in elderly, which is also taken into consideration, while multiple drug therapy prescribed. Research workers have clinically evaluated drug combination for various classes" cardiovascular agents, diuretics, anti-hypertensive in geriatrics. The combination choice depends on disease state of the patient.

Recent trend of manufacturing ODTs^[4]

The technologies used for preparation of oral dispersible tablets include lyophilization, molding, direct compression, cotton candy process, spray drying, sublimation and nanonization. These methods are produced on the principles of increasing absorbency and/or addition of the super-disintegrants and the water-soluble excipients in the tablets.

Table-1: Some examples of recently prepared oral dispersible tablets ^[5-10]

Sr. No	Drug	Excipients use
1	Candesartan cilexetil	Indion 204, tulsion 339, primogel, micro crystalline cellulose, magnesium stearate
2	Lovastatin	Sodium starch glycolate, cross povidone, croscarmellose
3	Levocetirizine dihydrochloride	Kyron T-134, talc, colloidal silicon dioxide, sodium starch glycolate, microcrystalline cellulose, crospovidone
4	Diclofenac sodium	Mannitol, crospovidone, microcrystalline cellulose, sodium starch glycolate, aspartame
5	Meclizine HCL	Explotab, tulsion 334, Eudragit E100
6	Efavirenz	Crospovidone, aspartame, croscarmellose sodium, sodium starch glycolate, magnesium stearate, microcrystalline cellulose pH 10

Characteristics of oral dispersible tablets ^[1,4,11,12]**Ease of administer oral route:**

Delivery systems are easy to administer and handle leads to better patient compliance. Generally, elderly people experience difficulty in swallowing the conventional dosage forms i.e. tablets, capsules, solutions and suspensions, because of tremors of extremities, bitter taste and dysphagia. Oral Dispersible tablets may offer a solution for these problems.

Taste of the medicament:

Mouth dissolving delivery systems usually contain the medicaments in taste masked form. This delivery system dissolves/disintegrates in patient's mouth, thus releasing the active ingredients which come in contact with the taste buds and therefore, taste masking of the drugs become critical to patient compliance.

Hygroscopicity:

Several Oral Dispersible dosage forms are hygroscopic and cannot maintain physical integrity under normal condition from humidity which calls for specialized product packaging.

Friability:

In order to allow oral disintegrating tablets to dissolve in the mouth, they are made of either very porous and soft- molded matrices or compressed into tablets with very low compression force, which makes the tablets friable or brittle which are difficult to handle and often require specialized peel-off blister packaging.

Mouth feel:

Mouth feel is essential and patients should receive a product that feels pleasant. If any large particle from the disintegrating tablet remains insoluble or slowly soluble in saliva, could lead to an unpleasant and gritty feeling. It can be overcome by keeping the majority of the particles below the detectable size limit-range. In some cases, certain flavors can imbibe an improved mouth feel perception, resulting in a product that is perceived as being less gritty, even if the only change is the flavors. Effervescence can be added to aid disintegration and improve mouth feel by reducing the "dryness" of a product.

Various techniques used in preparation of ODTs ^[11,13]

Various technologies used in the manufacture of oral dispersible tablets consist of following:

Direct compression:

Direct compression characterizes the simplest and most cost-effective tablet manufacturing technique. This method can now be practical to the research of ODT because of the accessibility of enhanced excipients mostly super disintegrants and sugar-based excipients. The mixture to be compressed must have suitable flow of the properties and cohere under pressure thus assembly pretreatment as the wet granulation is excessive. Limited drugs can be directly compressed into tablets of standard quality. The disintegrant addition technology is cost-effective and easy to implement at the industrial level.

Sublimation method:

The slow dissolution of the compressed tablet containing even highly water-soluble ingredients is due to the low porosity of the tablets. This volatile material is removed by sublimation separation to the behind as a highly porous matrix. Tablets manufactured by this method have generally disintegrated in 10-20 sec. Even solvents like cyclohexane, benzene can be used as pore-forming agents.

Freeze-drying or lyophilization:

A process in which water is sublimated as of the product after freezing is so-called freeze drying. Freeze-dried methods offer more quick dissolution than other available hard products. Freeze-dried forms offer more rapid dissolution than other available solid products. The lyophilization method imparts a smooth amorphous structure to the bulking agent and sometimes to the drug, thereby

improving the dissolution physical characteristics of the formulation.

Tablet Moulding:

Tablets produced by molding are solid dispersions. The physical form of the drug in the tablets can be determined by whether and to what extent it dissolves in the molten carrier. The drug can exist as discrete particles or microparticles dispersed in the matrix. The molded tablets shaped by compression molding are air-dried. As the molding process is employed usually with soluble ingredients (saccharides) which offer better mouthfeel and breakdown of the tablets. But molded tablets have low mechanical strength, which results in erosion and flouting during handling.

Spray drying:

The preparation limited hydrolyzed and unhydrolyzed gelatin as a supporting agent for the medium, mannitol as a bulking agent and sodium starch glycolate/croscarmellose as a disintegrant. For getting immediate dissolution this method is used, but this approach involves both high constant time of production and produces tablets of very poor mechanical strength. This then mixed with the active ingredient and compressed into tablets.

Cottoncandyprocess:

This process contains the formation of a matrix of polysaccharides by simultaneously action of flash melting and spinning. The matrix is then cured or partially recrystallized to provide a compound with good flow properties and compressibility. The candy floss can then be milled and blended with active ingredients and other excipients and subsequently compressed into ODT. However, the high processing temperature limits the use of this technology to the most stable compounds only.

Mass extrusion:

This technology contains softening the dynamic blend using the solvent mixture of water-soluble polyethylene glycol and methanol and ensuing removal of making softer mass through the extruder or syringe to get a cylinder of the product into even segments using a heated blade to form tablets.

Phase transition:

In this method mixture of the low and high melting point sugar alcohols as well as phase transition in the manufacturing method, is main for the creating ODTs without any difference in the apparatus. Tablet is prepared in two phases. ODT was prepared by decreasing powder comprising xylitol (melting point: 93-95 °C) and erythritol (melting point: 122 °C) and then heating at about 93 °C for 15 min. After heating, the medium pore size of the tablets was increased and tablet hardness was also improved. The increase of the tablet hardness with heating and the storage did not depend on the crystal state of the lower melting point of the sugar alcohol.

Nanonization:

The ionization process contains a reduction in the particle size of the drug to nano-size by milling technique. The drugs are stabilized against agglomeration surface absorption on selected stabilizers. This process is suitable for poorly water-soluble drugs.

Fast dissolving films:

It contains a non-aqueous solution having water-soluble film-forming polymers (pullulan, carboxy methyl cellulose, hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose, hydroxy ethyl cellulose, hydroxy propyl cellulose polyvinylpyrrolidone, polyvinyl alcohol or sodium alginate.), a drug and another taste-masking agent which are used to develop a film as the solvent evaporates. In the case of bitter-tasting drugs resin adsorbate or coated microparticles of a drug can be used in a film.

Selection of excipients^[13,14]

Following excipients were selected to fulfill the criteria of fast disintegrating tablets

PVPk-30:

Povidone solutions are incorporated as binders in wet granulation processes. It is also used as an aid in disintegration and dissolution. It is used as a solubilizer in oral and parenteral formulations and used to enhance dissolution of poorly soluble drugs from solid-dosage forms.

Micro crystalline cellulose (Avicel102):

It is widely used as a diluent in tablets/capsules. It is used in both wet granulation and direct compression processes also used as tablet disintegrant. It has both binding and disintegrant action.

Croscarmellose Sodium:

It swells 4-8 folds in 10 seconds. The cellulose derivative swells in two dimensions radially. In formulation of tablets, it may be used in both direct compression and wet granulation processes. When used in wet granulation croscarmellose sodium is added to in both the wet and dry stages of the process so that wicking and swelling ability can both be utilized.

Sodium Starch Glycolate:

Sodium starch glycolate is widely used in oral pharmaceuticals as a disintegrant in tablet and capsule formulations. It is generally used in tablets prepared by either direct compression or wet granulation process. The usual concentration employed in a formulation is between 2-8%. The disintegration occurs by rapid uptake of water followed by rapid and enormous swelling.

Sodium Bicarbonate (NaHCO₃):

Carbon dioxide generating agents like sodium hydrogen carbonate (NaHCO₃), it swells in the gastric fluid as it gets contact with the aqueous medium. Formation of carbon di oxide and entrapment of that gas into the polymeric gel causes swelling of the dosage form, resulting a bulk density less than 1. Then after, it then remains buoyant and floats in the gastric fluid resulting a prolonged gastric residence time. in a formulation is between 2-8%. The disintegration occurs by rapid uptake of water followed by rapid and enormous swelling.

Mannitol:

As a Diluent in tablets (10-90% w/w). It is not hygroscopic and used with moisture sensitive active ingredients. Mannitol is commonly used as an excipient in the manufacture of chewable tablet and mouth dissolving formulation because of its negative heat of solution, sweetness and mouthfeel.

Patented technologies for ODT formulation ^[11,13,15-19]**Zydis Technology:**

This technology involves softening the active blend using the solvent mixture of water-soluble polyethylene glycol, using methanol and expulsion of softened mass through the extruder or syringe to get a cylinder of the product into even segments using heated blade to form tablets. The dried cylinder can also be used to coat granules of bitter tasting drugs and thereby masking their bitter taste.

Durasolv Technology:

Durasolv is the patented technology of "CIMA" labs. The tablets made by this technology consist of a drug, fillers and a lubricant. Tablets are prepared by using conventional tableting equipment and have good rigidity. These can be packed into conventional packaging system like blisters. Durasolv is an appropriate technology for products requiring low amounts of active ingredients.

Orasolv Technology:

Orasolv Technology has been developed by "CIMA" labs. In this system active medicament is taste masked. It also contains effervescent disintegrating agent. Tablets are made by direct compression technique at low compression force in order to minimize oral dissolution time. Conventional blenders and tablet machine is used to produce the tablets. The tablets produced are soft and friable and packaged in specially designed pick and place system.

WowTab Technology:

Wow tab Technology is patented by "Yamanouchi Pharmaceutical Co. " WOW means "Without Water ". In this process, combination of low mouldability saccharides and high mouldability saccharides is used to obtain a rapidly melting strong tablet. The active ingredient is mixed with a low mouldability saccharide and granulated with a high International Journal of Pharmaceutical Erudition www.pharmaerudition.org May 2014, 4(1), 21-38 28 | P a g e ISSN 2249-3875 mouldability saccharide and compressed into tablet.

Flashtab Technology:

Prographarm laboratories have patented the Flash tab technology. Tablets prepared by this system consist of an active ingredient in the form of micro crystals. Drug micro granules may be prepared by using the conventional techniques like coacervation, micro encapsulation, and extrusion spheronisation. All the processing utilized conventional tableting technology.

Orodis Technology:

There are several technologies to consider for orally disintegrating tablets. Orodis® is compressed technology, beside a fast disintegration time in the mouth (15 to 30 seconds) it has many advantages against other technologies. Hard tablets, not fragile-easy to handle. No specific packing required, can be packaged in push through blisters Smooth mouth-feel pleasant taste-incorporation of taste masking agents and flavors All the materials meets USP and EP standards conventional manufacturing equipment-not difficult to transfer to final production site. Cost effective.

MeltEase Technology:

Newer technology developed by nutrition formulators, which allows table dissolution in less than five sec (average 400 mg tablet) this is the best mechanism available to ensure compliance and increase sales in two important markets, children and the elderly for many nutritional supplements at a very marginal development cost effect in specific formulations, including taste masking and sustained release on certain ingredients.

Frosta technology:

This technology is patented by Akina. Frosta technology utilizes the core concept of formulating plastic granules and compressing at low pressure to produce strong tablets with high porosity. The process involves mixing the porous plastic material with water penetration enhancer and followed by granulating with binder. The technology can be used for almost any drugs including Journal of Applied Pharmaceutical Science 01 (05); 2011: 50-58 aspirin, loratidine, caffeine, and folic acid, vitamins and dietary supplements. Melting time varies from several seconds to about 10 seconds depending on the formulation. (Giri et al., 2010).

Pharmaburst Technology:

Pharmaburst technology (SPI Pharma, New Castle, Delaware) uses off -the-shelf coprocessed excipients to create an FDT that, depending on the type of active and loading (up to 700 mg), dissolves within 30–40 seconds. The quantity of Pharmaburst™ required in a formulation depends on the active in the tablet. It is necessary to carry out initial studies on a formulation by varying the amount of Pharmaburst™ from 50 to 80%, depending on the desired mouth feel and disintegration time. The process involves a dry blend of a drug, flavor, and lubricant that are compressed into tablets on a standard tablet press with stock tooling. The manufacture process can be carried out under normal temperature and humidity conditions. The tablets can be packaged in blister packs or bottle (Kaushik et al., 2004).

Nanocrystal technology:

For fast dissolving tablets, Elan's proprietary Nanocrystal technology can enable formulation and improve compound activity and final product characteristics. Decreasing particle size increases the surface area, which leads to an increase in dissolution rate. This can be accomplished predictably and efficiently using Nanocrystal technology. Nanocrystal particles are small particles of drug substance, typically less than 1000 nanometers (nm) in diameter, which are produced by milling the drug substance using a proprietary wet milling technique. (Kaushik et al., 2004)

Evaluation parameters of oral dispersible tablets^[20,21-29]

Weight variation test:

If the drug forms greater part of the tablet, any variation in the tablet weight obviously indicates a variation in the active ingredient this test resembles weight uniformity test. 20 tablets were selected at random and average weights were determined. Then individual tablets are weighed and the individual weight was compared with the average.

Hardness:

Hardness of MDTs tablets were evaluated by using “Monsanto hardness tester”. Tester consists of a barrel containing a compressible spring held between two plungers. Lower plunger is placed in contact with tablet & a zero reading is taken. The upper plunger is then forced against a spring by turning a threaded bolt until the tablet fractures. As the spring is compressed, a pointer rides along a gauge in the barrel to indicate the force.

Friability:

Roche friability is used to measure the friability of the tablets. It rotates at rate of 25rpm. 10 tablets are weighed collectively and placed in the chamber of friabilator. In the friabilator, the tablets are exposed to rolling, resulting from freefall of tablets within the chamber of the friabilator. After 100 rotations (4min), the tablets are taken out from the friabilator and intact tablets are again weighed collectively.

Percentage friability is determined by using formula,

$$\text{Friability} = \frac{(W1 - W2)}{W1} \times 100$$

Where, W1=weight of tablets before test

W2=weight of tablets after test

Content Uniformity test:

Ten tablets were used in this test, where each one was crushed and transferred into a 100 ml volumetric flask. The flasks were brought to volume by phosphate buffer pH 6.8. The flasks were placed onto a sonicator till complete dissolution; 1ml of the solution was filtered through a Millipore filter of 0.45µm pore size then introduced into a 25 ml volumetric flask which was completed to volume by phosphate buffer. The absorbance of the solution was measured using a UV-visible spectrophotometer against the blank buffer. The tablets meet the test if the mean drug content lies within the specified range of the labelled potency. Invitro Disintegration test: The disintegration time was measured using disintegration test apparatus. One tablet was placed in each tube of the basket. The basket with the bottom surface made of stainless steel screen which was immersed in water bath at $37 \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$. The time required for complete disintegration of the tablet in each tube was determined using a stopwatch. To be complied with the Pharmacopeial standards, dispersible tablets must disintegrate within 3 min when examined by the disintegration test for tablets.

Modified Disintegration apparatus for Disintegration study:

Three tablets per batch were evaluated for disintegration time by employing a modified dissolution apparatus. Instead of the disintegration apparatus described in JPXII, a modified dissolution apparatus (JPXII paddle method) was employed. Simulated salivary fluid (900ml), maintained at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ was stirred with a paddle at 100 rpm. Disintegration time was recorded when all the fragments of the disintegrated tablet passed through the screen of the basket.

In-vitro dispersion test:

This test is performed to ensure disintegration of tablets in the salivary fluid, if it is to be used as an oral dispersible tablet. In-vitro dispersion time was measured by dropping a tablet in a measuring cylinder containing 6 ml of simulated salivary fluid of pH 6.8. Five tablets from each formulation were randomly selected and in-vitro dispersion time was performed.

Wetting time:

Ten ml of water-soluble dye, eosin solution is added to Petri dish containing five circular filter papers of 10 cm diameter. Tablets were carefully placed on the surface of the filter paper and the time required for water to reach the upper surface of the tablet was noted as the wetting time. The test results were presented as mean value of three determinations.

In-vitro Dissolution studies:

In-vitro dissolution studies of the mouth dissolving tablets were performed according to USP XXIII Type-II dissolution employing a paddle stirrer at 50rpm using 900 ml of simulated salivary fluid pH 6.8 at $37\pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ as dissolution medium. One tablet was used in each test. Aliquots of the dissolution medium (5ml) were withdrawn at specific time intervals and replaced immediately with equal volume of fresh medium. The samples were filtered through 0.22 mm membrane filter disc and analyzed for drug content by measuring the absorbance by UV-Visible spectrophotometer. Drug concentration was calculated from the standard calibration curve and expressed as cumulative percent drug dissolved. The release studies were performed in replicates.

Particle packaging index (PPI):

Particle packaging index was calculated on FDTs compressed to its maximum extend by modifying the method. It is an indicator of compactness of powder. The particle packaging index is a ratio of density of tablet to density of particles.

Moisture Uptake Studies:

Ten tablets from each formulation were kept in desiccator over calcium chloride at 37°C for 24 h. Then the tablets were weighed and exposed to 75% relative humidity (using saturated sodium chloride solution) at room temperature for 2 weeks. One tablet without super disintegrant as control was kept to assess the moisture uptake due to other excipients. Tablets were weighed and the percentage increase in weight was recorded. The results were presented as mean value of three determinations.

Tablet Porosity Measurement:

The mercury penetration porosimeter can be used to measure the tablet porosity which is a relative assessment of the degree of water penetration in the formulation, responsible for its fast disintegration.

Advantage of oral dispersible tablets ^[20,26]

1. Suitable for controlled/sustained Offers improved compliance and convenience to patients and prescribers.
2. It improves patient adherence and reduces the development of resistance in case of antimicrobials.
3. Simplifies the logistics of procurement and distribution
4. For Rapid drug delivery, ODTs are considered to be preferred dosage form
5. The drug is released quickly from this dosage form and gets dissolve in GIT without getting into the stomach, increased bioavailability can be achieved
6. ODTs are very convenient for administering to various classes of patients from disabled, travelers and busy people, who do not always have access to water.
7. Some drugs are absorbed from the pharynx and esophagus as the saliva passes down into the stomach; in such cases, the bioavailability of drugs is increased
8. No water needed
9. No chewing needs
10. Better taste
11. Release active
12. Allow high drug loading

Disadvantage of oral dispersible tablets (ODTs) ^[30,31]

1. Rapid drug therapy intervention is not possible
2. Sometimes may require more frequency of administration
3. Dose dumping may occur
4. Reduced potential for accurate dose adjustment
5. For properly stabilization and safety of the stable product, ODT requires special packaging
6. Usually have insufficient mechanical strength. Hence, careful handling is required
7. Sometime unpleasant taste and/or grittiness in mouth

Industrial applications of ODTs ^[2,4,32]

1. To develop an orally disintegrating dosage form and to work with existing disintegrants
2. To further improve upon the existing technology of ODTs
3. To optimize the blend of disintegrants or excipients to achieve ODTs
4. To select and develop proper packaging material and system for enhanced stability of the product and also develop a cost-effective product
5. To arrive at different taste-masking agents and prepare palatable route of administration thereby increasing patient compliance
6. To develop disintegrants from different polymers which are used as coating materials by certain modifications and use them for formulating ODTs.
7. **Marketed products:** The commercialized products of ODTs which are available in market are given in table-2.

Table-2: Marketed products of ODTs ^[2,32]

Sr. No	Brand Name	API Name	Manufacturer Name
1	Benadryl Fastmelt	Diphenhydramine	Pfizer
2	Cibalginadue FAST	Ibuprofen	Novartis Consumer Health
3	Mosid MT	Mosapride	Torrent
4	Orthoref MD	Rofecoxib	Biochem
5	OlanexInstab	Olanzapine	Ranbaxy
6	Rofaday MT	Rofecoxib	Lupin
7	Valus	Valdecoxib	Glenmark
8	Zyprexa	Olanzapine	Eli Lilly
9	Zomig ZMT and Rapimelt	Zolmitriptan	Astra Zeneca
10	Romilast	Montelukast	Ranbaxy lab. Ltd. New-Delhi, India

CONCLUSION

Oral dispersible tablets (ODTs) are innovative drug delivery systems and have potential advantages over conventional dosage forms, with their improved patient compliance, convenience, bioavailability and rapid onset of action. Though considerable research has been done in the formulation development and technologies for ODTs, more intensive investigations are to be carried out in this promising area to result in newer cost-effective technologies and better products. The potential of dosage forms is promising because of the availability of new technologies combined with strong market acceptance and patient compliance. The consideration takes place in technologies, pharmaceutical companies can take advantage of ODTs for product line extensions or for first-to-market products. All the information's collected above about the ODT gives a better scientific based understanding. With continued research and development of new pharmaceutical excipients.

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List of Abbreviation & Conflict of Interest:

- I. Oral Dispersible Tablets (ODTs)
- II. Food and Drug Administration (FDA)
- III. Volume of Distribution (V_d)
- IV. Cardiovascular System (CVS)
- V. Polyvinylpyrrolidone K-30 (PVP K-30)
- VI. United States Pharmacopoeia (USP)
- VII. European Pharmacopoeia (EP)
- VIII. Fast Disintegrating Tablets (FDT)
- IX. Multidrug Therapy (MDT)
- X. Gastro-intestinal tract (GIT)

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